

ROLE OF MONTELUKAST IN DICLOFENAC-INDUCED KIDNEY INJURY

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Diclofenac is the main trigger of nephrotoxicity and acute kidney injury (AKI) because it causes oxidative stress. Therefore, the aim of this study is to evaluate kidney injury biomarkers in diclofenac-induced AKI in rats. **Methods:** Eighteen Sprague-Dawley Male rats were used and randomly divided into three groups. Group 1 (n = 6): Rats treated with 0.5 % sodium carboxyl methylcellulose (PO) for 7 days. Group 2 (n = 6): Rats treated with single injection of Diclofenac (100 mg/kg, i.p). Group 3 (n = 6): Montelukast (20mg/kg, oral) for 7 days then at 7th day rats injected single dose of Diclofenac (100 mg/kg, i.p). Serum creatinine, Blood urea, Proteinuria, Creatinine clearance (CrCl), neutrophil gelatinase associated lipocalin (NGAL), kidney injury molecules (KIM-1) were estimated in three groups. **Results:** Diclofenac (100 mg/kg, i.p) caused substantial AKI by significantly reducing CrCl and raising blood urea and serum creatinine. Plasma levels of KIM-

1 and NGAL were considerably higher than the other kidney biomarkers, with high sensitivity and specificity for AKI. **Conclusion:** In diclofenac-induced AKI, KIM-1 level is more accurate, sensitive, and specific than the other renal biomarkers. For high-risk individuals, estimating KIM-1 and NGAL levels should be considered cornerstones of early AKI detection. Additionally, Montelukast demonstrated a protective effect in a diclofenac-induced renal damage model in rats.

KEYWORDS: Diclofenac, Acute kidney injury (AKI), Montelukast, nephrotoxicity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) are an essential part of treatment for many inflammatory and pain diseases because of their potent analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. Due to their clinical efficacy, a broad spectrum of patients utilizes them all over the world, both through over-the-counter and prescribed medications. They are therefore extensively utilized in both clinical and everyday life.^[1,2]

Diclofenac (DIC) is an example of the acetic acid class of NSAIDs. Diclofenac sodium works by preventing the cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzymes from synthesizing prostaglandins from arachidonic acid.^[3] DIC inhibits COX-1 approximately ten times more than COX-2, which significantly lowers prostaglandin (PG) activity to regulate afferent arteriolar tone. Inhibiting PG synthesis with NSAIDs may result in afferent vasoconstriction, which would limit renal blood flow and lower glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and hemodynamic acute kidney injury (AKI) since PGs enhance afferent arteriolar dilatation.^[4,5]

DIC's harmful effects on renal glomeruli and tubules are the cause of DIC-induced nephrotoxicity. DIC causes tubular dilatation, loss of brush border, and the development of glomerular lesions.^[6] Blood urea and serum creatinine, the conventional indicators of AKI, are thought to be low sensitive and poor specific in identifying the previous renal impairment. Therefore, novel biomarkers that are more sensitive and highly specific and provide information about the location of underlying renal damage were needed to detect the initial renal injury.^[7]

Urinary proteins are considered to be an indication of both acute and long-term renal impairment caused by nephrotoxic medications. High molecular weight proteins are normally transported and migrated from blood into the lumen of the nephron by the glomeruli, but in pathological situations, high molecular proteins can be found in the urine as a result of nephron failure.^[8] When it comes to the early identification of glomerular filtration failure and structural glomerular damage, high molecular proteins such as albumin, transferrin, and immunoglobulin G are more sensitive.^[9] In contrast, low molecular weight proteins are primarily reabsorbed at the renal proximal tubules. When low molecular weight protein concentrations are excessive, a nephron overload occurs that exceeds the proximal renal tubules' reabsorbing capacity, resulting in proteinuria as the re-absorption capacity malfunctions.^[10]

Cysteinyl leukotrienes (CysLTs), which are 5-lipoxygenase products of arachidonic acid, have been demonstrated to produce tissue injury with pro-inflammatory chemokines and other mediators. Antileukotriene drugs, also known as leukotriene receptor antagonists and synthesis inhibitors, are a type of anti-inflammatory medication that has been shown to be effective in treating a number of inflammatory disorders. Montelukast (MON), a selective reversible CysLT1 receptor antagonist, is used to treat asthma and has been shown to diminish eosinophilic inflammation in the airways.^[11,12] CysLT1 receptor antagonists, in combination with biosynthesis inhibitors, have been demonstrated to attenuate ethanol-induced stomach mucosal injury.^[13,14] and experimental colitis.^[15] Furthermore, we identified that MON improved microscopic damage and kidney function while protecting rats from renal ischemia/reperfusion injury.^[16] MON enhanced renal function in septic rats with AKI by inhibiting inflammatory mediators. Additionally, it decreases oxidative stress, which improves renal outcomes. It can also minimize the negative effects of apoptotic progression following renal injury by modulating apoptotic factor concentrations.^[17] These findings indicate that blocking CysLT1 receptors may slow the inflammatory cascade and alleviate oxidative damage caused in AKI. This study used a rat model of DIC-induced AKI to investigate the potential protective effect of MON on kidney function and oxidant/antioxidant condition.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental animals

The "Medical Experimental Research Center," Faculty of Medicine, Mansoura University, Egypt, supplied eighteen male Sprague-Dawley rats weighing between 200 and 250 grams. Rats were kept on a 12-hour light/dark cycle, fed free food and water, and kept in plastic cages at a temperature of 25°C. The National Institutes of Health (NIH) requirements for animal care and procedures were followed, and the "Animal Care and Use Committee" at Mansoura University in Egypt authorized them. The code number for these procedures is PHARM.MS.24.09.102.

2.2 Chemicals and drugs

Diclofenac Sodium was obtained as **Voltaren** ampoule from NOVARTIS Pharma AG. (CH). **Montelukast** was obtained as **Asmakast** 10 mg tablets from Minapharma (Egypt).

Montelukast was dissolved in 0.5 % sodium carboxyl methylcellulose. All other chemicals are of high analytical grade.

2.3 Experimental protocol

- Rats have been divided into three groups at random, with 6 rats in each group:
- **Group 1, control group:** given 0.5 % sodium carboxyl methylcellulose (PO) for 7 days.
- **Group 2, Diclofenac group:** given single dose of Diclofenac (100 mg/kg, i.p).^[18]
- **Group 3, Diclofenac + MON20 group:** given Montelukast (20mg/kg, oral) for 7 days then at 7th day rats injected single dose of Diclofenac (100 mg/kg, i.p).^[19,20]

2.4 Sample collection and preparation

All of the rats were housed in metabolic cages for a 24-hour period after receiving a dose of diclofenac. Urine samples were taken on day eight, centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, and the supernatant was kept at -80 °C to measure proteinuria and urine creatinine. Thiopental sodium (40 mg/kg, i.p.) was then used to put the rats to sleep. Blood was drawn from the retro-orbital venous plexus, centrifuged for 15 minutes at 4000 rpm, and the serum was then kept at -80 °C to quantify blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and creatinine. For later biochemical and molecular investigations, the left kidney was separated, weighed, and homogenized in phosphate buffered saline (10% w/v, pH 7.5).

2.5 Determination of kidney function biomarkers

A quantitative kinetic method assay kit from SPINREACT, Carretera Santa Coloma, Spain (Cat No.: MD1001111, Creatinine–kinetic kit) was used to analyze urine and serum creatinine in order to estimate CrCl using the following formula.

$$\text{CrCl (ml/min)} = \frac{\text{urinary Cr (mg/dl)} \times \text{urine volume (ml)}}{\text{serum Cr (mg/dl)} \times 1440}$$

Additionally, commercial assay kits from (SPINREACT, Carretera Santa Coloma, Spain, Cat No.: TK14041, Urea–reagent liquid kit) were used to quantify BUN and urine protein colorimetrically.

2.6 ELISA assays

According to the manufacturer's instructions, Kidney Injury Molecule (**KIM, Cat.No: MBS355395, MyBiosource, USA**) and neutrophil gelatinase -associated lipocalin (**NGAL, Cat.No: MBS2504748, MyBiosource, USA**), were assessed in renal homogenate using commercially available rat ELISA kits.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Mean \pm SD is used to express data. GraphPad Prism software (GraphPad Software Inc. V8, USA) was used for statistical analysis, graphing, and curve fitting of ELISA standard curves. Significant differences were indicated by P-values < 0.05 . One-way ANOVA was used to evaluate the differences in parametric data between groups, and the Tukey multiple comparisons test was used as a post-hoc test.

RESULTS

2.8 Effect of montelukast on serum creatinine

DIC administration alone induced a significant elevation in serum creatinine compared to the control group ($P < 0.05$, Figure 1 A).

Rats received injections of MON 20 orally for 7 days, followed by a single intraperitoneal injection of DIC on the 7th day, had significantly elevated serum creatinine level compared to the control group, while MON 20 group showed a significant reduction of serum creatinine compared to DIC group ($P < 0.05$, Figure 1).

Figure 1.

2.9 Effect of montelukast on BUN

Figure 2 illustrated that DIC group resulted in a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in BUN compared to control group. Rats received oral injections of MON 20 for 7 days, followed by a single intraperitoneal injection of DIC on the 7th day, had significantly increased BUN level compared to the control group. Besides, MON20 group resulted in significant reduction in BUN compared to DIC group. ($P < 0.05$, Figure 2).

Figure 2.

2.10 Effect of montelukast on proteinuria

DIC group showed a significant increase in proteinuria compared to control group. MON 20 group resulted in a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) in the level of proteinuria compared to control group. Besides that, MON 20 caused a significant elevation of proteinuria compared to DIC group ($P < 0.05$, *Figure 3*).

Figure 3.

2.11 Effect of montelukast on creatinine clearance

DIC group significantly reduced creatinine clearance compared to control group ($P < 0.05$, *Figure 4*). MON 20 group resulted in a significant increase in creatinine clearance compared to DIC group. No significant difference was observed between Control and MON20 groups.

Figure 4.

2.12 Effect of montelukast on KIM-1

DIC group resulted in a significant increase in kidney injury molecule-1(KIM-1) level compared to control group as it is a sensitive AKI biomarker. MON 20 group showed a significant increase in KIM-1 compared to control group but a significant decrease in KIM-1 compared to DIC group ($P < 0.05$, Figure 5).

Figure 5.

2.13 Effect of montelukast on NGAL

DIC administration significantly increased Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin (NGAL) level ($P < 0.05$, Figure 6). MON 20 group resulted in a significant elevation of

NGAL level compared to control group, while caused a significant reduction in NGAL level compared to DIC group.

Figure 6.

Figure legend

Figure 1: Impact of montelukast on serum creatinine.

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast.

Figure 2: Impact of montelukast on BUN

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast, BUN: blood urea nitrogen

Figure 3: Impact of montelukast on proteinuria.

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast.

Figure 4: Impact of montelukast on creatinine clearance.

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

CrCl: creatinine clearance, CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast.

Figure 5: Impact of montelukast on KIM-1

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

KIM-1: kidney injury molecule-1, CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast.

Figure 6: Impact of montelukast on NGAL

The results are shown as means \pm SD (n = 6 rats/group). Mean values were compared using one-way ANOVA, followed by post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparison test.

* Significance at P <0.05 vs CTR group. # Significance at P <0.05 vs. DIC group.

NGAL: Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin, CTR: Control, DIC: Diclofenac, MON: Montelukast

3 DISCUSSION

This study showed severe DIC-induced AKI, which was revealed through an elevation in SCr, BUN, and proteinuria accompanied by a reduction in CrCl compared to the control group in the experimental rats, showing impaired renal function as supported by *Alabi et al.*^[21] and *alAlkuraishy et al.*^[22] MNT's protective effect in this study was demonstrated in the serum, as raised levels of BUN, SCr and proteinuria were significantly lower than those caused by the diclofenac alone in accordance with *Suddek et al.*^[23] and *Kokate et al.*^[20] consequentially, montelukast resulted in a significant elevation of creatinine clearance compared to DIC group.

DIC administration raises kidney-related inflammatory responses, leading in tubular epithelial cell injury and subsequent upregulation of KIM-1 and NGAL, both of which are sensitive indicators of acute kidney injury. These signs develop earlier than traditional kidney function tests, demonstrating DIC-induced nephrotoxicity at the molecular and cell levels.^[22,24] In this investigation, DIC administration caused substantial tubular damage, as

demonstrated by elevations in kidney injury by elevated KIM-1 and NGAL in accordance with *alAlkuraishy et al.*^[22] and *Greite et al.*^[25]

MNT has an ameliorative effect in DIC-induced AKI as indicated by significant reduction in the KIM-1 level compared to diclofenac group which supported by Abdulredha et al.^[17] Additionally, MNT reduced DIC-induced kidney injury as indicated by significant reduction in plasma level of neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL) which supported by Wu et al.^[26]

5. CONCLUSION

The kidney injury molecule-1 KIM-1 serum level is more accurate, sensitive, and specific than the other renal markers in diclofenac-induced AKI. Estimating KIM-1 and NGAL plasma levels should be regarded as the cornerstone of early AKI detection in those who are at higher risk. In addition to, Montelukast possessed a protective effect in diclofenac-induced kidney injury model in rats.

6. Patents

Author Contributions: Nada S. Kamal: Writing original draft, Writing-review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. Omnia A. Nour: Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, corresponding author. Manar A. Nader: Writing-review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Ethical Approval: All animal experiments have been performed in accordance with the Basic & Clinical Pharmacology & Toxicology (BCPT) policy for experimental and clinical studies.^[27] and was accepted by the Faculty of Pharmacy's Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (ACUC) at Mansoura University in Egypt (Approval no: PHARM.MS.24.09.102).

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data of the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Gani MA, Parveen P, Saha D. Usage and Prescribing Patterns of NSAID in Different General and Specialized Hospitals in Bangladesh. *Sch Acad J Pharm.* 2022; 9: 161-6.
2. Burukoglu D, Baycu C, Taplamacioglu F, Sahin E, Bektur E. Effects of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory meloxicam on stomach, kidney, and liver of rats. *Toxicology and industrial health.* 2016; 32(6): 980-6.
3. Verhoeven F, Totoston P, Marie C, Prigent-Tessier A, Wendling D, Tournier-Nappey M, et al. Diclofenac but not celecoxib improves endothelial function in rheumatoid arthritis: a study in adjuvant-induced arthritis. 2017; 266: 136-44.
4. Kam P, See AUL. Cyclo-oxygenase isoenzymes: physiological and pharmacological role. *Anaesthesia.* 2000; 55(5): 442-9.
5. Inoue T, Anai S, Onishi S, Miyake M, Tanaka N, Hirayama A, et al. Inhibition of COX-2 expression by topical diclofenac enhanced radiation sensitivity via enhancement of TRAIL in human prostate adenocarcinoma xenograft model. 2013; 13(1): 1.
6. Bickel M, Khaykin P, Stephan C, Schmidt K, Buettner M, Amann K, et al. Acute kidney injury caused by tenofovir disoproxil fumarate and diclofenac co-administration. 2013; 14(10): 633-8.
7. Li Y, Deng H, Ju L, Zhang X, Zhang Z, Yang Z, et al. Screening and validation for plasma biomarkers of nephrotoxicity based on metabolomics in male rats. 2016; 5(1): 259-67.
8. Hosohata K, Yoshioka D, Tanaka A, Ando H, Fujimura AJHR. Early urinary biomarkers for renal tubular damage in spontaneously hypertensive rats on a high salt intake. 2016; 39(1): 19-26.
9. Bazzi C, Rizza V, Olivieri G, Casellato D, D'Amico GJJON. Tubular reabsorption of high, middle and low molecular weight proteins according to the tubulo-interstitial damage marker N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase in glomerulonephritis. 2015; 28(5): 541-8.
10. Park CH, Yokozawa T, Noh JSJTJON. Oligonol, a Low-Molecular-Weight Polyphenol Derived from Lychee Fruit, Attenuates Diabetes-Induced Renal Damage through the Advanced Glycation End Product-Related Pathway in db/db Mice. 2014; 144(8): 1150-7.

11. Wallace JL, Beck PL, Morris GP. Is there a role for leukotrienes as mediators of ethanol-induced gastric mucosal damage? *The American journal of physiology*. 1988; 254(1 Pt 1): G117-23.
12. Damtew B, Marino JA, Fratianne RB, Spagnuolo PJ. Neutrophil lipoxygenase metabolism and adhesive function following acute thermal injury. *The Journal of laboratory and clinical medicine*. 1993; 121(2): 328-36.
13. Carsin H, Barges L, Stéphanazzi J, Paris A, Aubert P, Le Béver HJP-b. Inflammatory reaction and infection in severe burns. 2002; 50(2): 93-101.
14. Wallace JL, McKnight GW, Keenan CM, Byles NI, MacNaughton WKJG. Effects of leukotrienes on susceptibility of the rat stomach to damage and investigation of the mechanism of action. 1990; 98(5): 1178-86.
15. Konturek SJ, Brzozowski T, Drozdowicz D, Beck GJ, D, sciences. Role of leukotrienes in acute gastric lesions induced by ethanol, taurocholate, aspirin, platelet-activating factor and stress in rats. 1988; 33(7): 806-13.
16. Şener G, Şehirli Ö, Velioğlu-Öğünç A, Çetinel Ş, Gedik N, Caner M, et al. Montelukast protects against renal ischemia/reperfusion injury in rats. 2006; 54(1): 65-71.
17. Abdulredha A, Majeed M. Renoprotective Effects of Montelukast in Sepsis-Induced AKI: Targeting the NF- κ B Pathway [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]. 2025; 14(660).
18. R S, S U. Diclofenac-induced biochemical changes in nephrotoxicity among male Albino rats. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*. 2018; 7(4): 640-3.
19. Gad AM, El-Raouf OMA, El-Sayeh BM, Fawzy HM, Abdallah DMJ, Job, toxicology m. Renoprotective effects of montelukast in an experimental model of cisplatin nephrotoxicity in rats. 2017; 31(12): e21979.
20. Kokate D, Marathe P. Evaluation of Effect of Montelukast in the Model of Streptozotocin Induced Diabetic Nephropathy in Rats. *Indian journal of endocrinology and metabolism*. 2024; 28(1): 47-54.
21. Alabi QK, Akomolafe RO, Adefisayo MA, Olukiran OS, Nafiu AO, Fasanya MK, et al. Kolaviron attenuates diclofenac-induced nephrotoxicity in male Wistar rats. 2018; 43(9): 956-68.
22. Alkuraishy HM, Al-Gareeb AI, Hussien NRJ, JoCMS. Diclofenac-induced acute kidney injury is linked with oxidative stress and pro-inflammatory changes in sprague-dawley rats. 2019; 5(3).

23. Suddek GMJF, pharmacology c. Montelukast ameliorates kidney function and urinary bladder sensitivity in experimentally induced renal dysfunction in rats. 2013; 27(2): 186-91.
24. Vaidya VS, Ozer JS, Dieterle F, Collings FB, Ramirez V, Troth S, et al. Kidney injury molecule-1 outperforms traditional biomarkers of kidney injury in preclinical biomarker qualification studies. 2010; 28(5): 478-85.
25. Störmer J, Gwinner W, Derlin K, Immenschuh S, Rong S, Jang M-S, et al. A Single Oral Dose of Diclofenac Causes Transition of Experimental Subclinical Acute Kidney Injury to Chronic Kidney Disease. *Biomedicines* [Internet]. 2022; 10(5): [1198 p.].
26. Wu S, Zhu X, Jin Z, Tong X, Zhu L, Hong X, et al. The protective role of montelukast against intestinal ischemia-reperfusion injury in rats. *Scientific Reports*. 2015; 5(1): 15787.
27. Tveden-Nyborg P, Bergmann TK, Jessen N, Simonsen U, Lykkesfeldt JJB, Pharmacology C, et al. BCPT 2023 policy for experimental and clinical studies. 2023; 133(4): 391-6.